

RETHINKING THE PUBLIC SPHERE AND THE REGULATORY TURN

AN INTERVIEW WITH PHILIP
SCHLESINGER

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Rethinking the Public Sphere and the Regulatory Turn: An Interview with Philip Schlesinger*

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Abstract

As digital platformization continues to disrupt traditional media ecosystems and transform the infrastructures of public communication, regulatory frameworks worldwide remain in a state of transition, grappling with the challenges posed by algorithmic governance, media fragmentation, and shifting power relations. In this interview, Philip Schlesinger elaborates on his use of the concept of a post-public sphere to theorise the structural rupture of rational-critical discourse in the digital age. He discusses the implications of these changes for democratic governance, the emergence of neo-regulation, and the evolving role of cross-agency regulatory mechanisms such as the UK's Digital Regulation Cooperation Forum (DRCF). This interview offers timely theoretical insights and empirical reflections that contribute to current debates on digital regulation, making it a valuable point of entry for those seeking to understand the institutional logic and geopolitical stakes of digital governance today.

Keywords

Post-public sphere, Neo-regulation, Digital regulation, Platform governance, State power, Digital Regulation Cooperation Forum (DRCF)

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Rethinking the public sphere in the digital age

Q: Why is the idea of a 'post-public sphere' an important focus for your research on neo-regulation?

Philip Schlesinger (P.S.): As my work has long addressed the relations between media, politics and democracy, my interest in regulation is just a different focus on a long-standing concern. I adopted the idea of a 'post-public sphere' because of changes in the media landscape in liberal-democratic states. This was the starting point for my work on digital regulation (Schlesinger, 2020). My focus has been on the shift from what's commonly called a 'legacy' media system (with the printed press, radio and television at its centre) to a hybrid system, in which older anchor media have mutated into digital forms while still conserving aspects of their earlier incarnations.

Alongside digital transformations, political and economic changes have challenged the institutional forms of liberal democratic states, and indeed, the survival of the democratic order. The digital revolution has brought about a fracture in the forms of communication, their circulation and modes of address, and types of audience reception.

A pivotal figure in debate on the public sphere is the German political philosopher Jürgen Habermas, with whose work I engage periodically. In a recent book, Habermas (2023) has underlined the importance of 'unregulated' exchanges between citizens and the epistemic threat of a post-truth political culture to democratic communications. A functioning public sphere requires a public constituted in ways that broadly respect the rules of the discursive game. In the Habermasian ideal speech situation the use of an argument that deploys evidence to warrant a judgement matters greatly. For Habermas, regulation has become a possible antidote for bringing order to a platformized society. But how regulation might work in this way is simply not explored. It is a gesture towards a possible solution that requires further investigation. I share some of Habermas's analysis but overall, it fails to recognise the depth of the crisis. We are experiencing not a transformation of the public sphere but its partial supersession. To name a *post*-public sphere insists on that recognition. The value of stressing the present 'post-ness' of the public sphere is that it registers the significance and profundity of present changes. My key point is that there is a *rupture* (Schlesinger, 2024).

Naturally, we should leave open the possibility of new power relations and rules of the game developing. The reconstitution of a re-imagined public sphere is not out of the question. Under present conditions, though, it is likely to take a strongly nationalistic and sovereigntist form, with its own complications and limitations.

Q: How does an analysis of the ‘post-public sphere’ shape your understanding of regulatory mechanisms in the digital era?

P.S.: I have engaged with a central question: what might regulation bring to the defence of the democratic order? While you need to understand theories of regulation, you also need an empirical sensibility regarding how things work. In this context, neo-regulation is connected to the post-public sphere because it is intended to perform a *defensive* role: it is about rules of conduct that aim to set negotiated boundaries while still securing space for critical forms of expression. At a time when an enhanced concern for national security is in the ascendant everywhere, there is always a risk of regulation tipping into censorship.

Influenced by Pierre Bourdieu’s field theory (1993), I also proposed the concept of a ‘regulatory field’ (Schlesinger, 2020). The key point is that we recognise how relations between states, regulators, the regulated, and interested parties (all of which deploy relevant expertise) are structured in and by power. Of course, how the regulatory field may be described in any given jurisdiction depends on the state form and the legal and political culture. What happens at the level of the state, and what is seen as characteristically and distinctively national, needs to be understood in the context of international relations. Understanding the regulatory field, therefore, requires a dual focus on the interactions between internal institutional logics and external power relations.

The regulatory turn and the UK’s exploration

Q: Could you explain what led you to propose the concept of ‘neo-regulation’?

P.S.: The regulation of digital space has come centre stage in many jurisdictions (Flew, 2021). Regulation varies from place to place but there are key driving forces: for instance, how the functioning of platforms relates to national security and defensive ideas of digital sovereignty, the often-divergent impact of social, moral and cultural demands regarding the regulation of content, and economic imperatives pursued by key big tech power brokers which intersect with, and shape, politics both nationally and globally.

I hit upon the ideas of ‘neo-regulation’ and a ‘regulatory turn’ in work with my colleagues Martin Kretschmer and Ula Furgał at the CREATE Centre for Regulation of the Creative Economy at the University of Glasgow. We examined the emergence of digital regulation as an increasingly distinct object. This new framing resulted from a public policy debate that covered a range of questions – notably, those dealing with online safety, competition in the marketplace, and how to handle tensions between safeguarding privacy and the trade in data (Kretschmer et al., 2022).

When we started our investigation in 2018-19 our focus was on the UK, which in a referendum held in June 2016 had voted to leave the European Union (EU). This decisive moment has been labelled 'Brexit'. We could not avoid a post-Brexit reappraisal of the British state's global position, which was high on the national agenda. That rethinking hasn't ceased, not least given the present turmoil of the tariff wars being waged by the US government. Will the UK's links with the EU deepen as those with the US begin to weaken?

When we began our research, the UK was in the process of resolving the kind of regulatory turn it was making. It also became clear that something innovative was happening in the regulatory space. Digital regulators had concluded that the scope of regulation must change, that to use the cliché – it couldn't be kept in silos because the very field of activity that was being regulated was mutating at pace. They needed to keep up with technological developments and their impact – to address how their increasing momentum was changing the very scope of regulation. The specific form that the regulatory turn took in the UK was shaped by a process of inquiry. A series of official reports set the parameters for debate. There were well-documented political pressures in play that gave further impetus to the emergent conclusion. Regulators had read the public policy terrain and understood the implications for the regulatory field.

So, you have a regulatory turn that is happening internationally, and then you have a new form of cooperative regulation emerging within it. I tried to capture this in a reconstruction based on the official paper trail and global developments in policy thinking that had influenced the setting up of the Digital Regulation Cooperation Forum (DRCF) (Schlesinger, 2022). In the next phase of our research, the analysis has been deepened and extended by socio-legal fieldwork on the DRCF (Kretschmer and Schlesinger, 2025). An external perspective on neo-regulation is being complemented by accessing an internal one. The underlying principle is that a micro-study of this kind, when properly constructed, provides an entry point for examining a set of relations that reveals the complex range of factors that constitute the wider regulatory field.

Q: Is the creation of the DRCF as a new regulatory consortium a significant policy innovation in the UK?

P.S.: 'Neo-regulation' refers to regulatory innovation – new practices invented for enforcing the public interest in novel circumstances. This contrasts with traditional regulatory models that employ single government agencies where the boundaries of legal competence are strongly prescribed.

The UK's DRCF was initially established by three regulators in 2020 during the Covid-19 pandemic. The agencies in question were the Competition and Markets Authority (CMA), the

Information Commissioner's Office (ICO), and the Office of Communications (Ofcom). In 2021, they were joined by the Financial Conduct Authority (FCA). All are bodies vested with statutory powers by the UK Parliament. The creation of the DRCF exemplifies 'neo-regulation' in practice: a distinctive governance framework whose operations required a specific label to capture its novelty and significance.

We have analysed how the DRCF, as a cooperative mechanism that crosses regulatory boundaries, has created space for itself to act as a 'brokerage agent' within the UK's pluralistic regulatory landscape. We have identified seven core functional activities undertaken by the DRCF: its role as a kind of think tank; its capacity building; the guidance issued to interested parties; its coordination of regulatory interventions or enforcement; the provision of services for regulated entities; and the pursuit of international networking and governance. Such activity may be seen as 'adding value' to established modes of regulation and as providing a rationale for the DRCF's invention and continued existence.

In the wake of the Brexit vote, the UK's neo-regulation reflects a specific national response to changed global circumstances. The establishment of the DRCF is a timely reaction to this dynamic environment. While the UK has been an innovator in devising this form of cooperation, other jurisdictions have followed the model. We should note the creation in 2023 of the International Network for Digital Regulation Cooperation (INDRC), whose present members – aside from the UK – are Australia, Canada, the Republic of Ireland, and the Netherlands, each of which has adapted the British model to its own circumstances.

Pluralistic AI regulation and emerging governance clusters

Q: To what extent do you foresee the DRCF expanding its mandate to encompass AI within its framework of cross-regulatory cooperation?

P.S.: How AI will fit into the UK's future regulatory picture is an open question. The DRCF has been a response to prevailing conditions and some of its work does address questions posed by AI: for instance, it has considered policy questions that arise from the use of algorithms and advised small-scale innovators through its experimental AI and Digital Hub.

The UK Government has set up an AI Security Institute, to inform governance and support its 'pro-growth' agenda. The regulatory landscape will change if a dedicated AI regulator is created.

How that body might articulate with the DRCF will also depend on how existing regulatory bodies mutually adapt their remits and collaboration.¹

Thinking beyond the immediate UK context, the policy choices made internationally by governments regarding AI rulemaking will vary from place to place and will be diversely sensitive to a gamut of interests; at any moment, they are also likely to be heavily influenced by prevailing geopolitical and geoeconomic considerations. There is a range of regulatory models located in different jurisdictions, and at present global governance seems a remote possibility. Of course, we should not preclude anything.

Q: How do you see the future of platform governance evolving globally?

P.S.: Only a brave soul would hazard a prediction. For instance, the once-fashionable view (Bradford, 2023) that common adherence to democratic values between the US and the EU would ultimately override differences of interest over digital regulation now looks extremely fanciful. We might, though, consider current conditions that are likely to set the scene in the immediate future.

These are turbulent times in which global competition between the US and China is at the forefront of our attention. Of course, President Trump's tariff campaign affects everybody everywhere, not just China and the US. The prospect of making global agreements on platform governance does not look very promising in this context. After all, regulatory concerns are deeply connected to the impact of tariffs, and we are presently witnessing the rapid decline of the so-called 'rules-based' order, which has dominated the globe since the end of World War II.

In the context of international trade, there are early signs that new relations between states are being initiated due to the tariff crisis. If these prove durable, novel collaborative spaces will emerge, and there will be convergent national interests that adopt common forms of action. However, such observations must be highly provisional.

In the context of international trade wars, digital regulation is unavoidably on the agenda (Mattelart, 1979; Daniels and Krige, 2022; Miller, 2022; Farrell and Newman, 2023). In a recomposing global context, analysing emergent clusters of governance where states' interests coincide will be an important focus for policy researchers. Certainly, globally dominant players' use of their political, economic and cultural power to shape and disrupt the scope of regulation within and between subordinate sovereign states is also of key relevance for research.

¹ Since this interview was given in spring 2025, various forms of 'regulatory coherence' and 'coordination' have persisted as the UK model. The DRCF is a key exemplar of this approach (Jones and Deakin, 2025).

Q: Does your early work still shape your interests?

P.S.: Your question has prompted me to review my main concerns. It is worth distinguishing between the topic analysed and the underlying issues addressed. I've always been interested in how the media work and are controlled. I began by looking at the production of news in the UK's iconic national broadcaster, the BBC, and it makes perfect sense for me now to research regulation, which in one key respect is another way of talking about modes of control of content. Of course, when I was doing fieldwork in newsrooms, I was aware of that control function and analysed it. Furthermore, my interest in how democracies deal with national security and how, in turn, that relates to different modes of communication, and their strategic uses has been longstanding and has reappeared in my most recent work on neo-regulation.

I began with a critical perspective on broadcasting policy and subsequently came to see it as a particular dimension of convergent media, communications and cultural policies. Relatively clear boundaries that once prevailed have largely ceased to be meaningful, not least when we prefix once-distinct policy areas with the term 'digital'. In its classic form (and this is still so in the digital age), broadcasting policy is centrally concerned with questions of culture, nation, and collective identity, especially how these relate to statehood and the chronic construction of a political community.

This interest has been congruent with my later work on European cultural policies and international audiovisual trade, subsequently shifting the scope to address and critique creative economy policy. Some of my earliest interests, therefore, later informed my work on Europe, which at one point concerned relations between national identities and the possibility of a supra-national European public sphere. I undertook that work during a high point of cosmopolitan optimism. I am now revisiting this question through the sober optic of how regulation relates to global trends towards national securitisation.

Finally, one theme that consistently reappears – and that, too, was in my earliest work – is the sociology of the locales in which various forms of expertise are deployed. These include the interface between journalists and their sources, modes of public intellectuality, the role of think tanks in policy debates, how cultural institutions work, academics as actors in public roles, and latterly, the organisation of digital regulation. In short, aspects of my early work have often played into issues pursued in my later research. And one thing I've never lost is the compelling taste for doing ethnography.

Q: Ethnography was once a central method in newsroom studies but is less common in China today. Is it still valuable?

P.S.: My first research project aligned with what was then the pioneering study of journalistic settings. I still value an ethnographic approach as highly relevant and productive for work in our field. The newsroom and editorial processes in legacy media have not ceased to be of great interest in the digital age but we need to take account of changed modes of news production, circulation and reception.

When I began media research, fieldwork in broadcasting focused on dominant systems of mediated communication located in central cultural institutions. Despite the radically changed media landscape, pursuing access for fieldwork in media organizations has not lost its relevance. For instance, it is still an illuminating way of investigating the management (or failure to manage) the chronic need for adaptive strategies to the demands made by rapid and continual change consequent on digitalization (Ryfe, 2012; Schlesinger and Doyle, 2015). The analysis of legacy media – which still matter despite a transforming landscape – remains highly relevant for any broad-based and nuanced understanding of how communicative power is distributed in different political regimes.

Both the press and broadcasting have made significant adaptations to media landscapes radically transformed by digitalization. Their content circulates more diversely, through podcasts, video platforms, search engines, and social media. The ways in which this occurs, the kinds of competition that ‘mainstream’ media encounter, and the diverse modes of consumption and interpretation of their content, are at the heart of the present crisis of the mediated public sphere. Crucially, formerly established and taken-for-granted claims to professionalism and expertise by media organizations and their workforces have been challenged by the rise of various kinds of ‘citizen journalist’, and latterly ‘influencers’ – the latter being a capacious category that encompasses numerous kinds of content production; notably, it particularly valorizes market-driven presentations of self. In this context, ethnography’s scope clearly needs to be extended to keep pace with contemporary transformations and research must address the crucial question of what now counts as journalism, what has driven these far-reaching mutations, and what their consequences are.

However, it’s not as though thinking beyond the newsroom tradition is completely new. It is certainly pre-digital! When I was working on crime reporting with Howard Tumber, we focused on source-media relations and underlined the limits of the previously dominant media-centricity in research (Schlesinger 1989; Schlesinger and Tumber, 1993). In our research on the criminal justice field, we needed to think relationally, to conceptualize how media reporting intersected

with unequally resourced actors. Those in positions of authority contended daily with a range of actors to seize and manage the news agenda. Official sources had diverse success and were not invariably structurally advantaged in defining the story.

That perspective was built on the critique of a structuralist fatalism which obscured the real dynamics of struggle. Although we recognized that the role of news sources had long been written into the script of earlier fieldwork-based studies, we found that its significance had not been fully theorized. To judge by the continuing use of that now venerable work, the position taken still resonates strongly. In the digital age, it is open to much fuller elaboration.

The relationship between mediated content and its audiences or users has been profoundly reconstituted by digitally driven change in processes of intermediation. The proliferation of non-institutional forms of content production in contention for audiences is based on the labour of unequally endowed sources which are competitively engaged in shaping the attention economy and therefore the configuration of communicative spaces. Contemporary contention for attention undoubtedly requires us to extend the scope of source-media analysis. It is still of direct relevance for how we understand the post-public sphere's impact on political life and culture.

Q: Is ethnography relevant for research on digital platform regulation?

P.S.: You would hardly expect me to think it is *not* relevant! In some respects, the contemporary ethnography of digital regulators has similarities with the heyday of news production studies. Generally, such regulators are based in and legitimized by central institutions, established or licensed by states, and endowed with powers underpinned by law. Of course, this is not the only possible regulatory model, but it is a key one in most jurisdictions. How regulators work varies greatly in accordance with the state form and the extent to which a jurisdiction's regulatory system affords a measure of autonomy and discretion to rule-enforcement. In the context of the post-public sphere in democracies, as legacy media decentre, I would contend that regulation is assuming greater centrality. It now bears the weight of increased expectations among governments and publics. Effective enforcement has the tough role of resolving a range of difficult, sometimes intractable, problems.

A widely held view in the academic field is that access for ethnographic research on journalism has become more difficult to obtain (Paterson et al., 2016). It would seem to be equally tricky in the field of regulation. It appears that the fieldwork-based analysis of platform regulation is presently in its infancy. However, recent publications based on doctoral research do show that a new generation is beginning to address this issue.

Yanling Zhu (2022) recently explored how uncertainties deriving from the shifting regulatory regime enforced by China's National Radio and Television Commission were addressed by a wide range of figures working in the television industry and major platforms. The state's regulatory focus on maintaining ideological boundaries in nationally produced content was central to her analysis. In a quite different political framework, Robert Gorwa (2024) observed that platforms were not inclined to supply interviewees, nor were governments cooperative. He interviewed officials, industry figures and civil society actors in Germany, New Zealand and the United States. Such studies show that there can be context-dependent workarounds in producing analyses of regulatory practice.

Has my current work on digital platform regulation been ethnographic, in the classic sense of observing social activity in a specific site (Atkinson, 2015)? To a very limited extent, yes, because the DRCF's Chief Executive opened the door to Martin Kretschmer and me to interview her team. This decision followed a series of academic events that were important in building regulators' confidence in our research integrity. Most interviews took place at the London headquarters of Ofcom, the Office of Communications, the key content regulator, which is where the DRCF core team is based.

I know the locale very well, as I was a member of Ofcom's Content Board, and prior to that, chaired its Advisory Committee for Scotland. But crossing the threshold this time led to a completely different take on the same milieu. It is one thing to sit on a committee focused on transacting regulatory business and quite another to research a workplace, even if it is a very brief 'immersion' (Olivier de Sardan, 2015).

The DRCF occupies a distinct space in Ofcom's premises on the south bank of the River Thames. During a week in October 2024 our interviews (both face-to-face and virtual) took place on site. Shortly thereafter, we had virtual follow-ups with those team members whom we could not meet on the first occasion. Alongside a carefully scheduled series of interviews that was the spine of our activity we had informal conversations and encounters. Being in a milieu is indispensable for conveying a sense of how things work.

To conclude, let me return to your question. So far, our research on digital regulators has involved a mix of methods and settings. If we apply a strict criterion, it has been marginally site-specifically ethnographic. Still, in addition to the interviews conducted at Ofcom there has also been a series of encounters and conversations with key regulatory players in settings such as a conference and a series of roundtables. On the basis of such experience, as well as in principle, I have no doubts about the value of an ethnographic approach for research on digital platform

regulation. It's been tried and tested in journalism studies – and indeed in a range of cultural organizational settings – and it's no less productive in a regulatory milieu. That's hardly surprising, is it?

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